

Mobile Learning App In The Covid-19 Crisis Among High School Students In Zimbabwe: Construction Of New Learning Conditions

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 26, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 24, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Zimbabwe, COVID-19, High School, Mobile Learning</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4633715</p>	<p><i>This paper discusses the challenges faced by learners of rural areas in Zimbabwe in the context of the global COVID-19 pandemic and suggests the adoption of a mobile app to mitigate the lack of resources for online learning. The paper is framed in bricolage, a theory that calls for creativeness and making use of the available materials to address vulnerabilities. Participatory action research was used to generate data from learners and teachers and the thematic approach was used to analyze data. Strategic sampling was used to identify participants for the study. The study sought to respond to two questions: What are the challenges faced by learners from rural areas with online learning? and How can the developed app assist to bridge the gap of lack of resources? We found that COVID-19 has worsened the plights of the learners from rural areas in Zimbabwe and increased the poor and rich divide. The paper argues that the mobile app developed has the impetus to address learning challenges faced by learners from rural areas and mitigate challenges of exclusion in teaching and learning.</i></p>

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has changed the way of life for many countries in the world. It has reimagined the world in a lens that could not have been thought of before the outbreak in Wuhan. Researchers have confirmed that the predominant measures against the spread of COVID-19 are social distancing, self-isolating, and prohibiting people from gathering in large numbers (Krishnakumar & Rana, 2020). Consequently, the traditional face-to-face teaching mode has been temporarily halted, forcing schools to engage in online teaching and learning as a way to contain the spread of COVID-19. However, while the idea of going online is noble and seemingly the only viable option for many countries, it does not resonate well with rural schools who over the years have remained behind in infrastructure and development to contain the online learning. Rural communities face various vulnerabilities which might derail efforts to ensure learning takes place through online means. To buttress this point, Avila and Gasperini (2005, p. 22) argued that people from rural areas lack access to socio-economic amenities such as quality education, good health services, transport, marketing facilities, and even electricity. People from rural often live nomadic lives – they are pastoralists and fishermen (Avila & Gasperini, 2005, p. 22). Thus, rural schools also confront a number of unique issues: geographic isolation, human capital shortages, and a rapidly changing economy (Chuong & Schiess, 2016). To further buttress this point, Du Plessis and Mestry (2019) argued that governments find it more difficult to supply quality education services in rural areas, and various factors weaken the quality of learning and teaching in South Africa's rural areas. Dieltiens (2008, p. 40) argued along the same lines, that "rural schools certainly have problems particular to them; predicaments which require systemic effort and creative ideas most. Rural areas already face tremendous barriers to high learner attainment and operate in less than favourable policy environments". Thus, COVID-19 has once again reminded these rural communities how vulnerable and deprived they are, especially with economic activities being halted (Ebrahim, Ahmed, Gozzer, Schlagenhauf, & Memish, 2020).

To circumvent the challenges of COVID-19, online learning has become the new normal, where the expectation is that learners and students are ready to embrace the online learning as a new way of living. While the idea is noble, seemingly the alternative is true for rural communities: it excludes learners from rural areas who have limited or no access to resources to ensure the success of the online learning. To this end, the learners from rural areas compared to their urban counterparts are excluded from the teaching and learning, which may further worsen the poor performance among the learners from rural areas in Zimbabwe. To accelerate the problem, World Bank (2020) argued that very few classroom teachers, especially in rural contexts, have received training in online instructional approaches and tools. In light of this, the paper is, as argued by Nkoane (2013, p. 113), "opposed to any classroom practices that undermine the rights of rural learners." Thus, the paper argues that there is a need to put strategies in place to improve the working conditions of teachers and the teaching at rural schools, improve learner achievement across the rural areas of Zimbabwe, and ensure a better

future for and development of human capital in rural contexts (Du Plessis & Mestry, 2019). Informed by the bricolage approach, we developed a mobile app which can be used by teachers and learners from rural areas to facilitate online learning. We saw this as the ideal approach since many households have cell phones which can support a learning app and which does not consume high volumes of data ensure low-tech data consumption. The approach to develop the mobile app resonates well with the observation by Shibeshi (2006, p. 12), that the solutions implemented should respond to the needs of teachers and learners from rural areas, and should consider their diversity – agro-ecological, geographical, and socio-economic standing. Through this, as Amry (2014) suggested, it will be ensured that e-learning goes beyond the classroom walls, allowing the teacher and the student to interact beyond distance and time constraints.

The paper is arranged as follows: theoretical framing, methodology, findings and discussions, and recommendations.

Theoretical framing: Bricolage

Bricolage is a concept first considered by French anthropologist Claude Lévi-Strauss in 1967 as a part of his exploration of the nature of sense-making in some societies (Vanevenhoven, Winkel, Malewicki, Dougan, & Bronson, 2011). We believe bricolage is relevant for the forgotten child in the rural setting because it advocates that people can construct something out of the little that is available, whether resources or systems, to achieve new goals (Aagard, 2009; Mahlomaholo, 2013). Thus, people informed by bricolage use all available knowledge, of immediate interest or outdated, within or outside of themselves, to solve a given problem (Louridas, 1999), which in this case is the unavailability of online learning materials in rural contexts and expensive data to support online teaching and learning. Furthermore, bricolage refers to the processes by which people acquire objects from across social divisions to create new cultural identities (Phillimore, Humphries, Klaas, & Knecht, 2016, p. 8). It is indeed true that the forever-marginalized learners and teachers from rural areas through embracing the bricolage approach can reimagine ways through which they can acquire new identities, and thereby break away from deprived learning conditions exacerbated by the global COVID-19 pandemic. We argue as such because bricolage allows for the combining of resources and systems for new purposes. It thus serves as a mechanism to drive the discovery of innovations which take the form of new “services” from existing resources (Duymedjian & Rüling, 2010; Jenlick, 2007).

All societies have basic mobile devices which can be exploited to ensure learning processes. Hence, the theory of bricolage calls for people to look beyond the ordinary and harvest and explore natural resources or available resources such as cell phones to change their circumstance and, in this case, improve teaching and learning among learners from rural areas in the context of COVID-19. Bricolage is convenient for this study because it enables the adaptive design process that is necessary for resilience and makes finding solutions to problems more achievable through use of critical resources or social systems (Vanevenhoven et al., 2011). In short, we couched this study in bricolage since it elicits solutions that emerge from ordinary processes, such as locally available resources. In addition, it offers a more optimistic outlook (Masten, 2001), which is not expensive, and has the impetus to address the lived realities of teachers and learners from rural areas during the global crisis.

Methodology

We chose participatory action research (PAR) methodology because it is an approach that encourages active participation of affected people to construct their new identities. The approach has an underlying philosophy that states that the people with the problem can suggest effective solutions for their problem. Another reason for using PAR for this study is that it “investigates the actual practices and not abstract practices and learning about the real, material, concrete, and particular practices of particular people in particular places” (Kemmis & McTaggart, 2007, p. 277). By doing so, PAR “identifies the rights of those concerned by the research, and empowering people to set their own schemas for research and development, thereby giving them tenure over the process” (Cornwall & Jewkes, 1995, p. 1674). Furthermore, PAR reveals and challenges conditions of injustice (Loewenson, Laurell, Hogstedt, D’Ambruso, & Shroff, 2014, p. 14), such as the move to online learning when learners from rural areas have no access to resources to support online learning. In short, we used PAR as it is a methodology which avoids univocal research representations, and promotes the adoption of techniques from multiple perspectives, voices, and sources to solve composite class challenges (Rogers, 2012).

The snowball or chain method was used to recruit participants, whereby participants were requested to identify other possible participants who could provide useful data for the study (Onwuegbuzie, 2007). The participation of the group members was guided by two research questions, namely: What are the learning challenges faced by rural learners in Zimbabwe in the context of COVID-19 and online learning? and What elements should a mobile app have to support learning in rural contexts? It is the responses to the second

question that necessitated the development of a mobile app to assist the teaching and learning. To respond to ethical considerations, we assured participants that pseudonyms would be used to cover their identities. We furthermore assured them that no one was obliged to participate in the study, and that they could decide to withdraw from the study for any reason (Fritz, 2008, p. 7). To collect data, we created a WhatsApp group with the ten participants for discussions over five days, where we reflected on the two questions for two hours a day in trying to establish the best features the mobile app should have to support learning in a rural context. The data generated through PAR were subjected to the thematic approach suggested by Laws, Harper, and Marcus (2003, p. 395), which comprises the following steps:

Step 1: Reading and rereading all the collected data: We read and reread the data from the discussions so as to obtain the views of the participants.

Step 2: Drawing up a preliminary list of themes arising from the data: We identified and arranged major issues and themes according to the two main research questions of the study.

Step 3: Rereading the data. We checked if the themes we had identified accurately represented what the participants had said, and that they related to the research questions.

Step 4: Linking the themes to quotations and notes: We linked the themes that emerged from the data to various scholarly views.

Step 5: Perusing the categories of themes to interpret them: In the interpretation of data, we remained cognizant of the research questions.

Step 6: Designing a tool to assist in discerning patterns in the data in order to triangulate and determine the patterns during data analysis.

Step 7: Interpreting the data and deriving meaning: Here, we mainly highlighted the research findings and arranged material according to categories premised on or guided by the research questions.

To ensure the validity of the findings, we conducted member-checking, during which process we presented the analyzed data that had been thematized to participants to obtain confirmation that the data responded to their lived experiences in the context of COVID-19, specifically teaching and learning using online platforms (Birt, Scott, Cavers, Campbell, & Walter, 2016; Bygstad & Munkvold, 2007; Gunawan, 2015).

In the following section, we present data gleaned during the WhatsApp discussions with participants.

Findings and discussions

Challenges faced by learners from rural areas in the COVID-19 crisis

This section presents findings for research question one. The underpinning observation from the findings is that rural schools continue to suffer poor, indeed worse, learning conditions overall compared to their urban counterparts (Czerniewicz & Brown, 2014). Four major themes were discovered which are seen as major impediments to online learning among learners from rural areas. These are discussed next.

Lack of online devices

It was noted that most learners and teachers from rural areas lack devices that support online learning. It emerged that for many countries, online learning seems to be the only way to address the trajectories of the COVID-19 pandemic. This is, however, underpinned by a wrong assumption that resources are available to support the online learning. The following participants noted the challenge associated with online learning with reference to lack of devices:

Jackson: Here in Lupane, we do not have any devices to support online learning; no Wi-Fi, no working laptops available at the schools, so even reaching the learners is impossible and hard.

Pearson: We hear a talk of online, but no one is telling us how the process would be done since we do not have the material to use. With the lack of online device, we need to accept that a year has been lost here in rural areas, for both the teachers and learners.

Part of the contributing factor to the lack of devices in rural schools is the fact that most rural communities face acute poverty compared to those in the cities. Thus, poverty shapes attitudes towards school (Stelmach, 2011), and propels people to find essential devices for supporting online learning. In the same vein, Du Plessis and Mestry (2019) argued that poverty is rife in many African countries and this has serious implications for the provision of quality education. Rural schools face severe challenges that are unique to their environment. In addition, as argued by Mulford and Johns (2004), rural areas are generally remote and relatively underdeveloped. As a result, many schools lack the necessary physical resources and basic infrastructure for sanitation (Mulford & Johns, 2004). Consequently, many rural households cannot afford to purchase online devices due to poverty, thereby affecting any attempts to mitigate the COVID-19 crisis through online learning. In short, the finding here is that online learning can only be possible when all learners and teachers have access

to online devices such as laptops, smart phones and iPads, among other devices. However, the current situation suggests that poverty impedes the purchasing of online devices, consequently affecting the move to online learning.

Lack of qualified and experienced teachers in blended/online training

The second challenge that was discussed by the group of participants was the lack of qualified teachers in most rural areas affecting the execution of curriculum packages. In fact, because of poverty and lack of resources to support learning in many rural areas in Zimbabwe, there has been an increase in out-migration by teachers in search of better schools. According to Jenkins, Reitano, and Taylor (2011), rural schools remain understaffed due to the high turnover of more experienced staff. Thus, the inability of schools in rural communities to attract and retain qualified educators affects their ability to provide a quality educational experience to learners within the community (Rude & Miller, 2018). Consequently, rural schools are left with either unqualified or inexperienced teachers who must devise strategies to promote learning during the COVID-19 crisis. Regarding this crisis, participants noted the following:

Mzolo: Most of the schools in the area have been deserted by teachers due to difficulties; thus, some of the schools have unqualified teachers employed by the school development to assist learners and such teachers are not in a position to embark on online learning as an alternative approach during the COVID-19 crisis.

Peter: We have learners that cannot read and write even though they're in secondary school. More so, the unavailability of qualified and experienced teachers in some schools, the move to online under such circumstances, worsen the plights of students who are already various challenges

It is clear from the above that some teachers are not qualified and experienced to teach online, which affects the noble idea of online learning. To this end, we agree with the observation by Schwartz (2006, p. 450), that "curriculum writers, with all good intentions, have compiled volumes of well-conceived educational action plans, choosing specific materials and activities for their pre-conceived target, curriculum receivers, students, only to find that the curriculum users, teachers, are not prepared for the innovations". In addition, World Bank (2020) pointed out that the students or teachers who will be able to make the best use of online learning are those who are already competent in and knowledgeable about using technological tools to support their learning, online sources in particular, who have sufficient access to good bandwidth and connected devices, and who are supported by their family and peers. Therefore, since online learning is a new phenomenon for most students and teachers in rural communities, it follows that there is need for a drastic approach to address the lack of skills by teachers to conduct online learning. Since it appears that teaching and learning is slowly but surely moving towards the direction of online learning, made urgent by COVID-19, there is need for major investment in online learning for both teachers and learners. Thus, in the spirit of curricular justice, we argue that children from rural areas deserve high-quality teachers who understand the importance of place, value their life worlds, and build appropriate teaching and learning opportunities (White & Reid, 2008). The success of this lies in the provision of qualified teachers with experience in online learning, or major investment in the training of teachers in online teaching.

Expensive data

The research also revealed that one of the challenges that derails the use of online learning among learners from rural areas is data costs. Cognizant of this challenge, many countries have moved towards the provision of free or affordable data to support online learning during the COVID-19 crisis. Other countries have also moved to zero-rated applications such as GlobalProtect to ensure that the challenge of data costs is addressed. However, Zimbabwe has not moved along this direction due to deprived economic situations. Furthermore, the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education has not issued a statement on how the challenge of data costs can be addressed, yet online learning is expected by both teachers and learners. The below sentiments by the participants reveal the challenge at hand:

Ngamla: The few teachers and learners with devices are struggling because data is very expensive and teaching all subject via online would be a nightmare.

Siza: Data is a serious process; it is very expensive and there is no provision from the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education to address the challenges we are encountering with data. The success of online is the availability of cheap data.

The fact that schools operate at the nexus of socio-cultural, political, and economic events, expensive data impacts success of teaching and learning (Stelmach, 2011). thus, the right direction would be major investment in free data to support online learning.

Lack of learning apps

The last major challenge affecting online learning in rural Zimbabwean schools as found by this study is lack of online learning apps within the Zimbabwean curriculum. It is this challenge that necessitated the need for this paper to design a learning app that can support learning in the context of COVID-19 and even beyond. During the discussions, the participants noted the following:

Dazy: I think teachers and learners are not against online learning; we need support only and availability of learning packages which contain the subjects we teach and resources recommended by the ministry at zero-rated.

Zanda: There is need for the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education to design mobile learning app that has the subjects we teach so that learners and teachers can interact with the material. The applications should be compatible with Android phones which seems many have here, then online learning can at least begin. Without the mobile learning app, online in rural areas is something that cannot be imagined now and in the near future.

The suggestions by the participants were very instrumental in conceptualizing an app that supports learning in rural contexts. It is these teachers, parents, and learners from rural areas who tend to bear the brunt of marginalization and the negative impact of social crises. We wanted to turn their gaze away from the challenges affecting them and work with them to address these issues as this is likely to yield more positive fruit than simply doing research about and on them (Moletsane, Mitchell, De Lange, Stuart, Buthelezi, & Taylor, 2009, p. 10). This resonates well with the argument that people with problems are better placed to suggest the solutions that can address their lived realities.

In the following section, we present the app which was designed as a result of this research to support learning in the context of COVID-19.

Essential elements of mobile learning app

This section addresses the second research question which related to ...

Figure 1. The designed app with list of subjects studied in rural schools

Figure 2.* The designed app showing links to different subjects that can allow teachers and students to interact

Discussion on findings and designed mobile application

Designing the app was necessitated by the need to promote and distribute quality and affordable education among learners from rural areas. As postulated by Bouhnik and Deshen (2014), a mobile app creates and contributes to a conducive learning environment among learners through creating an atmosphere that supports interaction, sharing of content, and intense collaboration among peers. The distribution of quality of education is essential and has positive consequences. The developed app thus attempts to ensure quality in the distribution of an education service. (Connell, 2012). While the app can also work in urban schools, we designed it with teachers and learners of rural areas in mind, cognizant that rural contexts require more attention (Stelmach, 2011) since they have been over the years deprived of development and resources compared to towns and cities. The formulation of the mobile app was also informed by the need to ensure that justice and equity are recognized and respected not only in the context of crises but in all circumstances. We agree with the observation by Mag, Sinfield, and Burns (2017), who stated that inclusive education is a child's right, not a privilege. As such, any approach to education during COVID-19 must be premised on respect for human rights. In respecting the rights of all students, no child should be left behind due to geographical location. All learners are important; thus, we also included them and the teachers in the development of the mobile app. In so doing, we agree with the observation by Oloruntegbe and Collins (2011), that particularly teachers and learners who have first-hand experience of the realities of online learning in the context of COVID-19 initiate successful reforms from the grassroots up (bottom-up). The developed mobile app to support learning in rural contexts is premised on the desire to create conditions under which distorted learning environments can be subverted, and a positive academic identity cultivated (Mahlomaholo, 2009). Ultimately, through this app, we may ensure that there is equality and equity in the school context. As alluded to by OECD (2012), equity can go hand in hand with quality; and reducing school failure strengthens individuals and societies' capacities to respond to recession and contribute to economic growth and social wellbeing.

Conclusion

Rural learning remains a challenge in many countries due to various challenges faced by both the teachers and learners. COVID-19 has once again revealed how much rural schools are deprived to support online learning. Having this in mind, the article discussed various challenges faced by teachers and learners from rural areas in executing online learning. The paper went on to discuss the designed app to address online teaching and learning. The developed app was designed based on input from the participants because PAR as the methodology of this study supports the views of the participants and acknowledges that those deprived have solutions to contribute to address their vulnerabilities. Such approach was in line with the need for curricular justice, and the need to respect learners and teachers from rural areas as a means to create equality and equity in

*The learning app also contains a section where the teacher can post voice notes or videos for the learners to listen and download. It also allows the interaction between the teachers and students

the context of crises. The paper ended by arguing that learners from rural areas are important and are included in sustainable development goals. The developed app may thus prove essential to ensure that the divide between learners from rural and urban areas is narrowed down, not only during the COVID-19 crisis but also for learning beyond the crisis.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the South African National Roads Agency Limited (SANRAL) and the National Research Foundation (NRF reference number: TTK: TTK200226506883)

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